

Oral presentation

Host plant affiliation of xylem-feeders in central Europe

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Abstract: Provoked by the first notification of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Europe, several countries aimed to acquire data on the presence of already confirmed as well as potential vector species of the bacterium present in Europe.

In Germany, vector surveys were carried out predominantly on plant species which are economically important in central Europe and known to be highly endangered by *X. fastidiosa* in the event of further bacterial spread, like grapevine, almond and cherry. Results are shown, which have been obtained from a three-year survey in the course of the project Xf-actors. The population dynamics of xylem-feeding species (spittlebugs, froghoppers and sharpshooters) were assessed in orchards (cherry and almond) and vineyards. Furthermore, the xylem-feeding activity of the most prevalent species on these plants was observed by EPG (Electrical Penetration Graph) to evaluate their potential vector-related risk as host for *X. fastidiosa* acquisition. The results will support an estimation of the transmission risk to specific crops under field conditions with a special focus on species able to transmit the bacterium, like *Philaenus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris*.